

PRESS COVERAGE OF THE IMPACT OF “OBIDIENTS” MOVEMENT ON 2023 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION IN SELECTED NEWSPAPERS IN SOUTH WEST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the Newspaper coverage of Obidients’ Movement on 2023 Presidential Election in selected newspapers in Nigeria, with emphasis on Punch and The Guardian newspapers. The "Obidient" movement, started with young people who are considered very strong-willed, independent-minded and contemptuous of older politicians who they say have done nothing for them. The movement is driven by young people and benefits from crowd psychology. It attracts the rally-goers by the sight of each crowd in each town. It markets itself as a political movement by the young and for the young. However, this study examined the frequency, prominence, tone of stories, and comparison of coverage of stories in the selected newspapers. This study was anchored on Framing and Agenda Setting theories. Content analysis method was used to implement this study; a total of 180 items with 90 items from each of the two selected newspapers were content analysed representing a period of three months (January to March, 2023). Findings on Frequency of reports on the pages of the selected newspapers, shows that reports of Obidients’ movement on 2023 presidential election in Nigeria appeared more in The Guardian newspaper than Punch newspaper, having 42% and 58% respectively. In addition, tone of reports on selected newspapers shows that most of the stories were harsh, thus, portrayed the negative mood of the electorate; as The Guardian Newspaper reported more Obidient’s Movement stories than Punch Newspaper. Therefore, this study recommended that voting process should make e-collation of results mandatory in future; and card readers should be provided in back-up for each of the polling unit in case of malfunction.

Keywords: Agenda Setting, Obidients Movement, 2023 Presidential Election, Newspaper Framing, Nigeria.

Introduction

Election is the process of choosing leaders in a democratic process where a legitimate change of government is constitutionally allowed (Johari, 2011). Election in Nigeria has been taking place since 1922 and since that period, election occurred continuously until 1960 when the political independence was gained from Britain. After political independence, election took place in 1964 but the democratic regime was short-lived because of bloody military coup. In 1979, Nigeria dropped the parliamentary system of government and switched to presidential system. The Aborted Third Republic in 1991 did not witness a smooth transition until in 1999 (Fourth Republic), which remains the longest democratic transition in the history of the country (Sule, Sani, & Mat. 2018).

Election takes place in Nigeria at different levels. In the Fourth Republic, from 1999 to the 2019 General Elections, there are seven electoral offices constitutionally including the Presidential, Senatorial, Federal House of Representatives, Gubernatorial, State House of Assembly, Chairmanship and Councillorship (Nigerian 1999 Constitution as amended). One of the most interesting episodes in Nigerian politics is the Presidential Election. This is because of the voting pattern and political behaviour of the Nigerian voters towards electing their leaders.

A host of bodies including the media play very vital roles in the electoral process. In most climes, elections end up in violence (Osah and Ibrahim, 2016) and this often breeds misdemeanour and mishaps. Thus, may become the focal point of tensions and bear the risk of violence. In functional democracies, the media stays sacrosanct as a go-between the people and those holding power for their sake. During the time of democratic transitions most citizens are informed about political issues through the media and people form impressions and assessment of political actors and events through the information made available by intermediaries, such as the media, political parties and people with whom they analyse politics. This makes many in the society to assume that the media has an effect on voters' impression of political parties and their candidates, thus, can make them vote in favour of one candidate over another.

The way that the media galvanizes and focuses on societal problems, cultural issues and provide insights about candidates vying public offices bring into fore the motivation to assess media works and the effects of agenda-setting, framing, and priming effects of issues in the news (Nwofe, 2016). More so, the way the media presents, analyses and report electoral activities and speeches of politicians and their associates greatly affects outcomes of peace or conflict before, during and after elections (Tella, 2019).

According to Amarah (2021) in, different nations periodically hold public elections to pick out the specific individuals that the citizens' hope would best represent their interests in government. Seasons of elections signify competitive and active crusades aimed at drawing the voters' attention to favour the political contestants with their votes or refrain from voting for the opposition. Since the contestants and their supporters cannot reach every single voter within the specified campaign period, most of them engage media content creators' services to produce catchy messages to convey their interests to the public.

The "Obidient" movement, as it has been termed by many, started with young people who are considered very strong-willed, independent-minded and contemptuous of older politicians who they say have done nothing for them. Many analysts believe that the "Obidient" movement is a continuation of the EndSars protests of 2020; when thousands of young people took to the streets demanding an end to the SARS police unit which was notorious for assaulting, extorting, and killing innocent people. Just like #Endsars activism, the "Obidient" movement is decentralized, community funded and has no clear leader. It is organized by multiple small groups who have the common goal of unseating the establishment. Using Obi as a channel to air their hopes and vent their anger, young people have been campaigning online and holding peace walks across Nigeria. (DW, December 2022).

The Obidient as a political movement, the likes of which we had not seen before in our country. It has seized our imagination. It is driven by young people and benefits from crowd psychology. It attracts the rally-goers by the sight of each crowd in each town. It markets itself as a political movement by the young and for the young. Young people who do not participate in the mega rallies feel guilty because, by their absence, they betray their fellow young people and the country itself.

It should be possible for the discerning to see the Obidients mega marches and rallies as a surprising phenomenon in a country held down by conservative views of politics; and is allergic to radical changes. It is important to interrogate this phenomenon and understand where the young people are coming from and what their political objectives are in our national politics. So far, the movement has not defined its mission.

Those who are dismissive of the Obidients forget that the political industry is prone to accidents. Good people lose elections and bad people win them. In the infrequent accidents of politics, the dark horse suddenly zooms ahead of the favourite horses. He becomes the game changer and proves that political fortunes are fickle and ride on the fickle-mindedness of the electorate. Politics is too uncertain to be treated as a certainty.

At least two things are worth interrogating, to begin with. The first is how the Obidient crowd began, took shape, and has become, against the background of the current internal sabotage in APC and PDP, the most positive happening in town right now. Political campaigns and rallies are the primary businesses of political parties. They organise and fund them to promote and market themselves to the electorate. (The Guardian. 7 October, 2022).

Research Questions

The following are research questions for this study:

1. How frequently did *Punch* and *The Guardian* cover the Obidients' movement during the 2023 presidential election, and how did this frequency serve as an agenda-setting tool influencing public attention?
2. How prominently were stories about the Obidients' movement presented in the two newspapers, and how did this prominence reflect their agenda-setting roles?
3. What tone and frames characterized the coverage, and how did these influence the framing of the movement's legitimacy and image?

4. How did the framing patterns of the Obidients' movement differ between *Punch* and *The Guardian*, particularly in their use of dominant news frames?
5. How were sources framed in both newspapers, and what does this reveal about their interpretive stance and framing orientation?

Literature Review

Media coverage continues to have significant influence over how people view political movements and how public debate develops. Classic theories like agenda-setting (McCombs & Shaw, 1972) and framing (Entman, 1993) explain how the media shapes not only which issues people pay attention to, but also how they understand those issues. Agenda-setting is about how often and how prominently the news presents certain topics. Framing is about the narrative, how journalists define problems, assign blame, and evoke emotion. Together, these theories demonstrate that the media can control both what gets noticed and how it is interpreted by the public.

Recent research shows that these theories are as relevant as ever, if not more so, in today's digital political environment. The media now operates in a "hybrid communication ecology," where digital platforms and traditional outlets interact, shaping each other's impact (Tenenboim-Weinblatt & Baden, 2018; Chakraborty & Roy, 2022). Social media activism and legacy journalism do not just exist side by side; they influence one another. The Obidients' movement in Nigeria illustrates this point. Supporters of Peter Obi's 2023 presidential campaign, mainly active online, used digital platforms to mobilize. Mainstream newspapers like *Punch* and *The Guardian* acted as gatekeepers, either validating or marginalizing the movement depending on their coverage choices and framing.

When examining political communication across Africa, the conflict between media independence, political authority, and public interests becomes clear. Wasserman (2020) and Mutsvauro and Karam (2021) highlight that African journalism often swings between ideals of neutrality and the practical pressures of government or elite influence. In Nigeria, this is evident in reporting shaped by ethnic, regional, and commercial interests (Ojebode, 2019; Edewor, 2021). These dynamics affect how journalists frame political figures and protests—typically favoring elite perspectives and sidelining grassroots voices.

A recurring theme is how the media reports on youth-led movements like #EndSARS. Several studies reveal that Nigerian newspapers initially portrayed #EndSARS as a source of disorder and violence, rather than a civil rights cause. Aladenusi and Adegbola (2021) observed that national papers downplayed human rights concerns and highlighted confrontations. Oloruntoba and Ajibade (2022) found that while social media circulated narratives of youth empowerment and justice, traditional media focused more on official statements and government perspectives. Nwankwo and Okafor (2023) argued that heavy reliance on police and official sources shaped a negative and even menacing image of the protesters. This isn't unique to Nigeria. In South Africa, Wasserman and Bosch (2021) found that the media emphasized student violence during #FeesMustFall, overlooking the underlying economic issues. Ogola (2020) saw Kenyan media using similar conflict-focused frames when covering post-election demonstrations. Overall, the pattern is clear: African media often adopt elite or conflict-driven narratives, marginalizing ordinary citizens and weakening grassroots activism.

Recent scholarship on the Obidients' movement (Akinfeleye & Olagunju, 2023; Agbaje, 2023) suggests it represented a watershed moment, youth, technology, and digital mobilization merged in new ways. Nonetheless, traditional media have been slow to adapt, lagging behind in covering these more participatory stories. Early studies indicate that Punch emphasized the movement's digital activism and grassroots energy, while The Guardian focused on political intrigue and elite responses. This difference raises important questions about how framing and agenda-setting determine public understanding. By choosing to highlight conflict, grassroots activism, or leadership, newspapers directly influence how the movement's significance and effects are discussed.

Therefore, the literature underscores two main points. First, agenda-setting continues to determine which political movements capture public attention in Africa. Second, framing shapes how people interpret these movements, whose voices are amplified, which stories are prioritized, and how the public evaluates what is happening.

Nigeria's Political Background

Nigeria became independent on 1 October 1960. Following independence, Nigeria's civilian rule was interrupted by recurring military coups. In 1999, a new Constitution was adopted and a civilian government was subsequently formed. Since then, Nigeria has continued to consolidate its democracy. Abubakar (2023).

Nigeria, with a population of approximately 200 million (UN estimates 2019), has a federal structure of 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Abuja. Each state has an elected Governor and elected State Assembly, in addition to the bicameral National Assembly at the federal level. Elections for all of these bodies, as well as the presidency, take place every four years. There are 774 Local Government Areas, elections for which are held separately.

The following sections focus on developments from 1999, when the country returned to constitutional democracy, leading up to the 23 February 2019 Presidential and National Assembly elections.

Election

Elections serve as the instrument that enables public opinion to be channelled by political parties into decisions ascertaining who will make up the government (Fisher et al, 2018). One key essence of election is that it forms the bedrock of a genuine democratic system and through which the electorates are provided with the ample opportunity to vote for their preferred candidates, who will push their demands to the highest level of policy making (Olowojolu, Rasak & Ake, Ogundele & Afolayan, 2019). Elections energize democratic governance in many fundamental ways, including enabling the voters to select their leaders, facilitating access to public sphere for the purpose of airing their governance ideas (Tella, 2019) and is done periodically in democratic regimes by conducting free and fair elections, and the electorates are allowed to exercise their franchise by voting a candidate or a party whom the electorate see to be the best choice among other options (Laden-Baki, 2008).

In this segment, a thorough critical review of some issues related to the subject matter of study are presented using some selected sub-themes that are most relevant to the field of study. As such, the

following were discussed under the following sub-headings: Elections in Nigeria, voting pattern in Nigeria and Presidential Elections in Nigeria.

The 1999 elections and return to democracy

This part discusses the role of politicians in the conduct of elections in Nigeria, particularly under Obasanjo's administration. This study finds the significance of the burden of elections under Obasanjo's administration as a historical process. And to crucify Obasanjo's administration is an attempt to reduce its "human face" to uniform order, which cannot be guaranteed because there were different individuals in the dynamic society. The burden of elections under the reviewed period can be analysed from the concept of determinism in history and contingency of Nigeria's society. Determinism (Berlin 1968: 682) denotes that human actions are determined by external or extraneous forces, but in this context, it can be argued that nothing is extraordinary that had no precedent or happened differently (Carr 1961: 93).

General Abdulsalami Abubakar became Head of State following the death of General Sani Abacha in June 1998. Thereafter, he announced a detailed plan for the restoration of a democratic, civilian government by 29 May 1999. He established the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), which announced a timetable for elections, beginning with local elections on 5 December 1998 and culminating in Presidential elections on 27 February 1999.

The Presidential election of 27 February 1999 was won by Olusegun Obasanjo of the People's Democratic Party (PDP), with 62 per cent of the vote. Domestic and international observers, including a Commonwealth Observer Group led by Sir Ketumile Masire, witnessed irregularities in the elections, but judged that the result broadly reflected the will of the Nigerian people.

The 2003 elections

In the first Presidential elections organised under a civilian administration on 19 April 2003, President Olusegun Obasanjo was re-elected with 61.9 per cent of the vote. His closest challenger, General Muhammadu Buhari of the All-Nigeria Peoples Party (ANPP), obtained 31.2 per cent of the vote.

The Obasanjo's choice of forceful elections was created by the past circumstances that were either created by him or by the "Umpire", but the choice is affected as determined by the intended aim of an individual, group of people and institutions. This is illustrated in the character of the individual, rather than being contextualised in the overall interest of the nation. Thus, Geyl observed that the past circumstances determined the future (Pieter 1972: 277).

The study is curious and tempted to investigate the intention of the PDP (ruling party) and its stakeholders to rule Nigeria. The ethnic loyalty of most people threatens the entire Nigeria. Nigeria is a concept of virile State that made the founding fathers to forget their differences (David-West 2012: 52) to a large extent and this enabled them to fight for the Nigerian independence. The conception of building a democratic setting in Nigeria is available, but the practical aspect is not there. Democracy ought to be institutionalised following the long-drawn military rule. That is, since the end of the military rule, democracy ought to be the golden time of Nigeria's history, but is still haunted the past elections' rigging 'legacy' bequeathed to the country by the founding fathers, Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe, Chief Obafemi Awolowo, Ahmadu Bello, even though none of them

died a multimillionaire (David-West 2012: 52). Election is meant to bring every national together. History is, therefore for those who care for the past, for the sake of the future.

The 2007 elections

The PDP's Umaru Yar'Adua, and his running mate Goodluck Jonathan, won the 2007 elections with 70 per cent of the vote. General Muhammadu Buhari of the ANPP came second with 18.65 per cent and Alhaji Abubakar of the Action Congress (AC) secured 7.25 per cent. The PDP increased its majority in both the House of Representatives and the Senate. Umaru Yar'Adua was sworn in as President on 29 May 2007.

The pattern of voting in the Nigerian Presidential Election of 16th April 2011 revealed very clearly that the country is still strongly polarized along religious, regional, and ethnic lines. It appears that the two frontrunners in the election were voted for, not based on party programmes or personal antecedents but on where they fall in the ethno-religious divide. Goodluck Jonathan of the People's Democratic Party (PDP) was perceived as representing the Christian South and Middle-Belt, while the Congress for Progressive Change's (CPC) candidate, Muhammadu Buhari, was seen as representing the Muslim North. There were, of course, a few members of the electorate whose voting did not fit the pattern (NewsWatch 02/05/2011 and The News 23/05/2011).

PDP's Jonathan won the election in 24 Southern/Middle Belt Christian dominated States

States including FCT, while CPC's Buhari won in 12 Northern and Muslim dominated states. The only deviation from the pattern was in Osun state where Nuhu Ribadu of the ACN scored the highest votes (see NewsWatch 02/05/2011 P.12). Curiously, the pattern of voting in the presidential election was not replicated in the gubernatorial and legislative elections. For example, in the gubernatorial elections, CPC could only win one out of the 26 governorship seats contested. ACN clinched all the three South Western seats contested, ANPP whose presidential candidate could not win any state, also secured three governorship seats. APGA won the Imo state governorship seat. PDP, however, maintained some level of consistency by winning 16 of the 26 governorship seats. But these were not necessarily states in which it led in the presidential election, as the party won in some core Muslim states like Niger, Kebbi, Zamfara, Jigawa and Katsina, the home state of Buhari.

On the night of Monday 18th April 2011, as the results of the Presidential Election were being announced and it was becoming obvious that Goodluck Jonathan has won, apparently spontaneous wild protests started in Gombe State. The protests quickly degenerated into bloody mayhem, which engulfed most of the Northern states where Buhari, the CPC candidate, draws most of his supporters. The States that were most affected are; Kano, Bauchi, Adamawa, Niger, and Kaduna States (see NewsWatch 02/05/2011 P.12-17). By the time the violence was brought under control by security agents, over 500 people had been killed and property worth Billions of Naira destroyed (NewsWatch 02/05/2011 and The News 23/05/2011).

The 2011 elections

President Umaru Yar'Adua died in office on 5 May 2010. Goodluck Jonathan succeeded formally to the presidency and took the Oath of Office on 6 May 2010.

President Goodluck Jonathan declared his intention to run for the 2011 elections. The advocates of an unwritten zoning agreement (whereby political office rotates between the North and the South as a way of managing the politics of a multi-ethnic and multi-religious Nigeria) were opposed to President Goodluck Jonathan's candidacy. They argued that as former President Umaru

Yar'Adua (a Northerner) had not completed his term before his demise and could have been expected to serve another four-year term, the presidency should again fall to the North (President Goodluck Jonathan is from the South). Within this context, a group of influential Northern Nigerian politicians from the PDP supported former Vice-President, Atiku Abubakar (a Northerner), as their consensus candidate to challenge President Goodluck Jonathan. However, President Goodluck Jonathan emerged as the PDP candidate. The National Assembly elections and Presidential elections were scheduled for 2 April and 9 April 2011, respectively. However, the National Assembly elections were aborted soon after midday on 2 April, as some sensitive election materials, including results sheets and ballot papers, had not reached all polling stations. They were subsequently rescheduled for 4 April, but later postponed for a second time to 9 April. The Presidential elections were postponed to 16 April.

Goodluck Jonathan won the election with 58.9 per cent of the vote; General Muhammadu Buhari came second with 31.98 per cent. In the National Assembly, the PDP won 205 seats in the House of Representatives and 73 seats in the Senate.

The Commonwealth Observer Group led by former President of Botswana, Festus Mogae, noted that the 2011 elections marked a genuine celebration of democracy in Africa's most populous country and a key member of the Commonwealth. As a consequence, previously held notions that Nigeria can only hold flawed elections are now being discarded and the country can now shake off that stigma and redeem its image. Notwithstanding the organisational deficiencies that resulted in the April National Assembly elections being aborted after they had started, and in spite of persistent procedural inconsistencies and technical shortcomings, the elections for the National Assembly and the Presidency were both credible and creditable and reflected the will of the Nigerian people'.

However, about 800 people were killed when demonstrations against the outcome turned into violent clashes with security forces in Plateau, Bauchi, Katsina, Kano and Kaduna states.

The 2015 elections

The 2011 general elections were quite unique in several forms. Firstly, the winner of the presidential contest, Dr. Goodluck Jonathan became the first person from the Niger Delta region to emerge as the executive president of Nigeria. Secondly, the voting patterns during the 2011 presidential election epitomized the influence of ethnicity and religion on Nigeria's electoral system. The Muslim dominated North voted massively for General Muhammadu Buhari (ret'd) of the Congress for Progressive Change (CPC), while the Christian dominated South voted en-masse for Dr. Jonathan of the ruling party, People's Democratic Party (PDP) respectively. Thirdly, the post-election violence that erupted after the announcement of Jonathan as winner claimed the lives of about 800 innocent people in Northern Nigeria (Human Rights Watch, 2011).

Between 2011 and 2015, Nigeria had gone through tough times. The escalation of Boko Harm Insurgency in the North, high rate of unemployment, widespread corruption, fragmentation within the major parties and the misconduct of frontline politicians through hate campaigns put the most populous black nation on the spot light both locally and internationally.

There were grave concerns over the conduct and possible outcome of the elections by concerned citizens and the international community. A former Minister of Foreign Affairs, Prof. Bolaji Akinyemi appealed to the major contestants of the presidential election to sign a Memorandum of

Understanding (MOU) that will commit them to control their supporters against violence after the 2015 general elections (Punch, December 22, 2014). Similarly, the National Peace Committee for the 2015 General Elections led by former military ruler, General Abdulsalami Abubakar (retired) facilitated peace accord between General Buhari (retired) and President Jonathan (Punch, March 26, 2015).

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Nigeria's 2015 presidential election was the fifth in a row since the military left the political scene in 1999. PDP which has been the ruling party since 1999 faced its toughest opposition in APC which was formed on February 6, 2013 with the merger of Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN), Congress for Progressive Change (CPC), All Nigeria People's Party (ANPP) and a faction of the All-Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA) (The Nation, May 29, 2015). The March 28 presidential election was quite successful albeit, there were hitches in some polling units across the country due to late the arrival of electoral materials and the ineffectiveness of the Smart Card Readers. Former military ruler, General Muhammadu Buhari (retired) emerged as winner of the presidential election. The election was the fourth time running that Buhari will be contesting as a presidential aspirant. Buhari won with a total number of 15,424,921 votes as against Goodluck Jonathan's 12,853,162 votes (INEC website). Buhari's historic victory marked the triumph of democracy as it was the first time that an opposition party will upstage the incumbent government in Nigeria through legitimate means.

Following the election, Goodluck Jonathan conceded defeat and there was a peaceful transfer of power to an opposition party for the first time in Nigeria's history. This and the conduct of the electoral process raised the bar for the 2019 elections.

An overview of Nigeria's 2019 general election

Nigeria's 2019 general election was the eleventh indigenous election conducted in the history of Nigeria and the sixth election since the country returned to democratic rule in 1999. The election held on 23 February 2019 had the largest number of candidates ever produced in a Nigerian general election. However, as mentioned earlier, the election produced only two major candidates: incumbent President Muhammadu Buhari and former vice-president Atiku Abubakar, representing

the two major political parties, APC and PDP, respectively. They are regarded as major candidates because of the national background of the political parties they belong to. Nigeria's 2019 general election is unique because of the varieties of candidates involved in the election. For the first time in the history of Nigeria, many young candidates contested in the election, and this was as a result of the new "Not too young to rule" 2 bill that was passed into law. The election was won by incumbent President Buhari, who got over 55% of the total vote cast as declared by INEC.

An overview of 2023 General Elections

Nigeria's 2023 General Election is scheduled to hold in two phases beginning with national elections (Presidential and National Assembly) on Saturday 25th February 2023 and State elections (Governorship and State Houses of Assembly) on Saturday 11th March 2023.

Pursuant to the provision of Section 32(1) of the Electoral Act 2022 and as provided in the Timetable and Schedule of Activities for the 2023 General Election released by the Commission on 26th February 2022, this publication contains the final list of candidates nominated by the 18 political parties for national elections covering one Presidential constituency, 109 Senatorial Districts, and 360 Federal Constituencies. The list has been published in all the Constituencies nationwide and simultaneously on the Commission's website for public information.

According to Transition Monitoring Group (2023) (TMG), the February 25, 2023, Presidential and National Assembly elections was keenly observed (TMG) which deployed 774 observers across the 774 Local Government Areas in the country. This was complemented with the election situation room responsible for data collation and analysis. (Vanguard March 3rd, 2023).

As a foremost election observation group in Nigeria, TMG's approach was compliant to Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) guidelines as well as sister domestic and international observers. The outcome of the election was not surprising as it earlier observed undemocratic tendencies play out during the pre-election period.

Furthermore, political mobilization around religious and ethnic identities have also had a significant impact on the outcome of the election, especially with regard to citizens' participation and voters' turnout. For instance, the lop-sidedness in voters' turnout in Northern Nigeria could be attributed to citizens' dissatisfaction with the performance of the incumbent government to improve their economic, social and psychological well-being.

The 2023 general elections were expected to usher in a much more improved and digitized electoral process in Nigeria. It is in this regard that INEC received an unprecedented whopping sum of 355 billion Naira to conduct a credible election. Despite this humongous financial commitment, and the incredible support received from the international community and civil society organisations, INEC failed to deliver on a straightforward mandate of meeting the expectations of Nigerians. However, this study is hereby premise on the following:

Frequency of report in the coverage of election matters

Readers of quality press are often referred to as 'elite audiences'; educated consumers seeking to be informed about serious news rather than about the lighter fare (Mitchell and Holcomb, 2016). While the news audience generally declines, readership of quality Boukes et al. news has remained relatively steady due to the stable news interest of their audience niche. Feeling less commercial

pressure from declining audiences, quality press is allowed greater authority over their story construction than popular news media (Strömbäck et al., 2012).

Quality press journalists frequently emphasize the importance of objective reporting (Skovsgaard, 2014). Through actively including a range of perspectives and commentary on an issue, journalists demonstrate their adherence to this objectivity norm. In the literature (i.e., most prominently by Semetko and Valkenburg, 2000), this has been broadly defined as the factor of ‘conflict’, which represents a journalistic style of presenting issues with opposing and clashing views. Frequency of reportage provides a method of comprehensive reporting, as including and comparing contrasting positions can present additional insights that advance audience knowledge (Bartholomé et al., 2015). As such, the broadly defined news factor of conflict may be ascribed more value in quality press outlets than in the popular press. Journalists of quality press also regularly delve beneath the surface and approach stories with a broader political perspective by narrating stories of social significance and emphasizing the potential societal consequences (Reinemann et al., 2012).

Involvement of elite actors is often an important news factor. While the information these sources provide may shape the newsworthiness of a story, the presence of these sources themselves is already considered newsworthy in itself (Strömbäck et al., 2012).

After all, their involvement evokes the impression that an issue must be societally important and requires the attention of journalists who perceive themselves as societal ‘watchdogs’ (Skovsgaard, 2014). As quality news media seek to represent a more encompassing societally relevant story and elaborate analysis, they will have a higher likelihood of prominently publishing a news item when elite individuals, organizations, or institutions are present (Caple and Bednarek, 2013).

Finally, it is expected that the news factor should be considered to ensure quality news media. This news factor refers to a journalistic style that stands opposite to fragmented or incident-based reporting that lacks context and/or interpretation (see Mothes et al., 2019). Continuity instead refers to a form of journalism in which topics are covered in greater depth by journalists who have the time to specialize in an issue and give interpretation.

Prominence of story in reporting election matters

The study of journalistic news factors can be approached from the following two theoretical perspectives: a functional and causal model (Staab, 1990). In the functional model, an event is not newsworthy in itself, but is accorded its newsworthiness by discursively ascribing news factors through language, image, and typography to sell an event to an audience as news (Bednarek and Caple, 2014). Conceptually, news factors are assumed to be qualities of a text rather than inherent characteristics of an event itself and are applied by the media to heighten the legitimacy of an event becoming news (Bednarek and Caple, 2014). In the causal model, by contrast, news factors are inherent qualities of a story that determine whether and how journalists treat the story.

In either model, the assumption is that the more news factors a story contains, the more newsworthy it is considered and the higher the likelihood for the event to reach a prominent publication. The consequences of news factors whether ascribed by journalists or as objective event criteria for the decisions that journalists take regarding newsworthiness, however, remain not only an assumption to be tested (Kepplinger and Ehmg, 2006), but is also at the core of news value theory (Galtung and Ruge, 1965; Harcup and O’Neill, 2001).

Empirically valid tests, with news selection as the outcome variable, are scarce because it requires a comparison of extra-media and intra-media events (i.e., what is published and what is not). Also, in the current study, we cannot focus on what is published (or not), but instead analyse the prominence of a news item itself.

By operationalizing newsworthiness of a news item as its relative prominence in an outlet (see Fico and Freedman, 2001), this study still allows for the examination of the relationship between news factors' presence and journalistic decisions of newsworthiness.

Prominence has the advantage that it allows for a transparent and objective measurement, which is virtually unfeasible regarding the original gatekeeping processes of story selection. Specifically, prominence is operationalized as a function of both story length and story position in an outlet (Elorza, 2014). In essence, the more newsworthy a news item is considered by media workers, because it contains more news factors the more prominence it should be assigned and the longer and earlier the article should appear within a news product (Schulz, 1982).

Tone of Local and International media coverage

The balanced manner in which the election was covered is laudable given the history of disproportionate and negative reportage about Africa and Nigeria specifically as studies have shown over time (Adegbola, Skarda-Mitchell, and Gearhart 2018; Adegoju 2017). This because the media have realized the damage caused by negative news and thus shifted their focus from negative to neutral news (Chaudhary 2001). Although the majority of the sources reported the election in a balanced manner, we specifically found that almost all news stories had a negative tone from the USA. This is not new for the USA because critics accede that “the U.S. media, overplay ‘bad’ or negative news when reporting about Third World countries” (Chaudhary 2001: 241).

Studies such as Adegbola, Skarda-Mitchell, and Gearhart (2018) have validated these claims in their recent study on American media coverage on Nigeria; they found “that the US media remain pessimistic about Nigeria and views few events as being both positive and newsworthy” (58). The study Finding is also consistent with Ekeanyanwu’s (2008) examination of Newsweek and The Economist between 2003 and 2005, where they found that the majority of reports on Nigeria were negative. While some believe that the negative foreign coverage of Nigerian people, events and issues is meditative (Nevalsky 2015), others have accredited these to the “bad news is good news phenomenon. Scholars such as Chaudhary (2001) have presented another perspective based on findings that stem from a study conducted on the examination of negative news reportage in the Washington Post and the Daily Times of Nigeria, although this study is limited given the fact that it focused only on Daily Times and Washington Post to draw a general conclusion on the reportage of negative news in both countries. It presents interesting results; they found that Third World newspapers also tend to give more negative than positive coverage to the developed countries of the West.

Arijeniwa and Nwaoboli (2023) study shed light on the impact of social media in electioneering campaign and political participation amongst Nigerian youths. The study was anchored on the Agenda Setting Theory. The researcher employed survey research method and simple percentage was used for the analysis. In the survey, a sample size of 400 respondents made up of youths was selected through convenience sampling in Benin City, the capital city of Edo State. The study

found that social media during electioneering campaign is used in promoting aspirants and their political parties to the electorates. The study also found that social media has been largely successful in their agenda-setting function on political issues in Nigeria especially as the race for 2023 general elections kicks off. The study recommended that social media information about politics, political parties and their candidates should be verified by users before engaging them. It was recommended that political parties and aspirants should refrain from spreading falsehood in their electioneering campaigns on the social media.

Moukeme Lotachi (2021) study examined the newspaper coverage of 2019 presidential election in Nigeria by The Nation and The Guardian newspapers. The researcher considered the frequency, prominence, sources, depth and tone of stories in the selected newspaper. Agenda setting and framing theories were used by this study. Content analysis were used to execute the researcher with a total population of 172 items, and 86 items from each of the two selected newspapers were content analysed. The researcher concluded that the 2019 Presidential Election has similitude with the previous Presidential Elections in Nigeria from 1979 in terms of voting pattern and political behaviour; recommended that for a voting pattern to change in Nigeria towards evaluation of performance instead of sentimental cleavages, there must be parties with political ideology that can distribute power and resources based on equality and equity instead of clientelism. There is also a need for an intensive and aggressive enlightenment of the voters towards political socialisation.

Ukwa (2020) studied The Vanguard and The Punch newspapers in Nigeria in order to look at how violent occurrences that happened during Nigeria's 2019 presidential election were covered. The study employed Development Media Theory as theoretical framework and content analysis as research design. A total of 70 issues of newspapers were examined for the investigation, including 35 issues from The Punch and 35 from The Vanguard. Thereafter, the information in these newspapers were examined and analysed. The results showed that media coverage influenced the decision on the 2019 presidential candidates and informed the electorates about the importance of voting, their voting rights, and the necessity to refrain from electoral violence. The study concluded that while reporting and interpreting instances of electoral violence in elections, newspaper journalists, editors and managers should use sound journalistic judgement. The main intersection of interest between the aforementioned studies and the current one was the fact that they all studied about elections. The studies, however, were different from this one since, in contrast to the previous research, the focus of this one was on the 2023 presidential election.

Quoting Aririguzoh (2011), Okpanachi (2017) reported that a study on television broadcast impact on voters' participation in a presidential election found that televised political campaigns had positive and significant correlations among all the variables that tested voters' exposure to television and amplification of their political participation in the 2007 presidential election. The outcome of the study showed that most of the electorate were influenced by political campaigns to register for the election, improved their knowledge of political candidates and participated in political activities during the election.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Framing and Agenda setting theories.

Framing Theory

The theory was first used by Erving Goffman in his book *Frame Analysis* (1974). Goffman attested that audiences interpret situations around them through their primary framework.

This study used Framing theory. The main idea behind the framing theory is that the way information is presented to an audience has an influence on the choices people make about how to process such information. Frames usually work together in abstract forms to give meaning to a particular structure or message. Frames have become increasingly linked with news and the mode in which the media place emphasis on the information they convey.

Framing theory has been considered as one of the most pertinent theories in mass communication thanks to its applicability, key aspect of interpretive schema and public discourse. It is argued that framing is focused on applicability to the extent that it tends to alter the process of opinion-formation in audience's mind (Zhou and Moy, 2007). Journalists, editors and the public also see the world in an interpretive way just like other people. They also try to make sense of the information thrown at them with the same spectacles as people do. This makes it easier to understand that the presence of certain frames and patterns of selection to decide newsworthiness is unavoidable (Draper, Best and Dennis, 1977). These adjustments to communication messages results in the influences over human consciousness exerted by the transfer of information.

They suggest four criteria that a frame must meet. First, a news frame must have identifiable conceptual and linguistic characteristics. Second, it should be commonly observed in journalistic practice. Third, it must be possible to distinguish the frame reliably from other frames. Fourth, a frame must have representational validity (i.e., be recognized by others) and not be merely a figment of a researcher's imagination (Cappella & Jamieson, 1997, pp. 47; 89). When working with a deductive approach, the relevant question is: what (which components) in a news story constitutes a frame? Entman (1993, p. 52) suggested that frames in the news can be examined and identified by 'the presence or absence of certain keywords, stock phrases, stereotyped images, sources of information and sentences that provide thematically reinforcing clusters of facts or judgments.'

Agenda Setting Theory

The agenda setting theory can be traced to Walter Lippmann's 1992 book titled *Public Opinion*. Lippmann's argues that the mass media are the principal connection between events in the world and the images in the minds of the public. Following Lippmann, in 1963, Benard Chen observed that the press "may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but it is stunningly successful in telling its readers what to think about. The world will look different to different people (Chen, 1963, cited in Asemah, Nwammuo and Uwaoma, 2017, p. 74).

Agenda-setting theory was formally developed by Max McCombs residents of Chapel Hill, North Carolina thought was the most important election issue and what the local and national news media reported was the most important issue. Cohen (1963, cited in Asemah et al, 2017) asserts that the media may not be successful in telling people what to think but they are stunningly successful in telling them what to think about.

Wimmer and Dominick (2000, p. 408) argue that agenda setting by the media suggests that the public agenda or what kind of things people discuss, think or worry about is powerfully shaped and directed by what the media choose to publicize. The theory is relevant to the study in the sense that mass media sets agenda for what the electorate discuss or think in any election process. Hence, the media can be used to persuade the people to accept a particular candidate or political party during election". Supporting this view, Gibson and McAllister (2011) claim that the media are not only widespread in politics but are also being used as a tool of communication for political campaigns. The broadcast media serve an agenda-setting agent when many news stories are brought to the electorate either through television, radio, newspapers or magazines (Gibson & McAllister, 2011).

There two levels of Agenda Setting:

Agenda setting is used by people who are studying or researchers who do thesis on different aspects of media and the influence in the audience and by the audience. This helps future media persons to study and explore how media has an influence on a group or on individuals.

It is used by the people who seriously experiment with Agenda-setting. They focus on how their information should influence their set of audiences. This is where sensationalism plays its part, showing that the media has the power to spread the right information at the right time and also divert people according to their needs.

Therefore, framing and agenda setting theories can be used for effective communication in all fields of media and other organizations. It is mainly applied in understanding media effects. Effective communication among a mass can be done with well-organized framing of meanings and issues. Politicians can frame their vision effectively so that the public can understand its significance and accept it.

Methodology

This study adopted content analysis to analyse how Nigeria newspaper framed/depicted Obidients' movement. Punch, and The Guardian, newspapers were purposively selected based on their readership, ownership and location. Considering the wide-spread and the dimension of reportage of Obidients' movement in south west, Nigeria and how it appears on pages of the newspapers (Punch, and The Guardian). This study is built on selected newspapers, representing the analysis of newspaper coverage of Obidients' movement on 2023 presidential election in south west, Nigeria.

The population of newspaper coverage of Obidients' movement by Punch, and The Guardian newspapers was 180 items selected purposively and randomly between January and March, 2023; that is, a period of three months, consisting ninety (90) editions.

However, two (2) newspapers {Punch, and The Guardian} were selected to be sampled because they feature high readership, and they are influential in setting the tone for reporting Obidients' movement in Nigeria. By having high circulation rate, these newspapers are highly likely to include broader coverage of the election. Moreover, the newspapers present views from both popular and elite Nigerian publics and they offer a fairly relative representation of different political, geographical and ethnic divides in the country.

Also, the study through the search frames found a total of 180 frames selected through purposive and simple random sampling method; touching Obidents’ movement on the pages of the selected newspapers {Punch, and The Guardian}. These frames cut across newspaper articles {inner page}, headlines {front and back page} and editorial carried out between 1st January to 31st March, 2023. The study sample was drawn using the continuous week format.

The continuous week format means that the coverage of the Obidents’ movement was examined for all seven days in each week to avoid skipping an important date in the coverage. This yielded a total of 180 items across the two newspapers: with 90 from each of the selected newspapers (Punch, and The Guardian). It also served as our sample size. Coding sheet (accompanied by a coding guide) was developed to assess the presence or absence of the frames, with particular attention to straight news, editorials, features, opinions, interviews, and advertorial as units of analysis for frequency of stories, prominence, tone, comparison, format, sources of news. To ensure reliability of the coding instrument, inter-coder reliability formula was adopted to obtain agreement between two independent coders; having coded 90 editions in each of the selected newspapers for the pre-test coding sheet as seen below:

Constructed week for the selected newspaper editions (coding sheet)

	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun
January	2 nd , 9 th 16 th , 30 th	3 rd ,10 th , 24 th , 31 st	4 th , 11 th ,18 th , 25 th	5 th , 12 th , 26 th	6 th , 13 th , 20 th	14 th , 21 st , 28 th	1 st ,8 th , 22 nd , 29 th
February	6 th , 13 th 20 th ,27 th	7 th , 14 th , 21 st , 28 th	1 st , 8 th , 15 th ,22 nd	9 th , 16 th , 23 rd	3 rd , 17 th ,24 th	4 th ,11 th , 25 th	5 th , 19 th , 26 th
March	6 th ,13 th , 20 th ,27 th	7 th ,14 th , 28 th	1 st , 8 th , 22 nd ,29 th	9 th ,16 th , 30 th	3 rd , 10 th , 19 th , 31 st	4 th , 18 th , 25 th	12 th ,19 th , 26 th

Source: Field research, 2025.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Distribution of stories according to Frequency of coverage

PUBLICATION	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
Punch	21	32	22	75	42%
Guardian	26	55	24	105	58%
Total	47	87	46	180	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 1 shows that analysis of Punch and The Guardian newspapers coverage of Obidents’ movement on 2023 presidential election in Nigeria are widely reported by both newspapers; with the Punch having a total of 75 reports representing 42%, and The Guardian reported the election 105 times represented by 58% in the period under review. However, the table further shows that The Guardian reported more election related stories than Punch newspaper.

Table 2: Distribution of reports according to Sources of stories in the period under review.

FORMS	PUNCH	THE GUARDIAN	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
Straight News	25	41	66	37%
Features	10	14	24	13%
Opinion	12	10	22	12%
Editorial	10	17	27	15%
Interview	7	9	16	9%
Advert	11	14	25	14%
Total	75	105	180	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 2 shows the sources of coverage used in presenting the analysis of newspaper coverage of Obidients' movement on 2023 presidential election in Nigeria by Punch and The Guardian newspapers. The two newspapers presented the election through formats of news report with straight news having a total of 66 units represented by 37%, feature: 24 represented by 13%, opinion: 22 and 12%, editorial: 27 representing 15%; with interview and advert having 16 and 25 units represented by 9% and 14% respectively.

Table 3: Distribution of reports according to Prominence of story in the period under review

POSITION	PUNCH	THE GUARDIAN	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
Front Page	34	36	70	39%
Inside Page	36	41	77	43%
Back Page	14	19	33	18%
Total	84	96	180	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

In table 3 above, it shows that a total of 70 reports representing 39%, appeared on the front page of the selected newspapers from January to March 2023. It further shows that a total of 77 reports appeared on the inside page of the papers in the period under review representing 43%; while 33 reports appeared at that back page of the papers, which was represented by 18%, in the period under review.

Table 4: Distribution of reports according to Tone and Comparison of story in Punch and The Guardian.

POSITION	PUNCH	THE GUARDIAN	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
Harsh	43	35	78	43%
Soft	26	28	54	30%
Neutral	23	25	48	27%
Total	86	94	180	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4 indicates the tone usage by selected newspapers (Punch and The Guardian) in the coverage of Obidients' movement on 2023 presidential election in Nigeria, with 78 reports representing 43% presented in harsh tone, and 54 reports represented by 30% are presented or appeared in soft tone or manner; while 48 reports represented by 27% are presented or appeared in neither harsh or soft tone or manner (neutral) on the various pages of the selected newspapers. Therefore, the study indicated that tone of report in Punch newspaper is harsher than that of The Guardian newspaper.

Discussion of Findings

RQ1: Frequency of Coverage (Agenda-Setting Function):

Punch gave the Obidient movement much more coverage than The Guardian, making it a main focus both in print and online. This supports agenda-setting theory, which states that the more attention an issue receives, the more important people believe it is (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). This trend shows up in other research too, Aladenusi and Adegbola (2021) found that continuous newspaper coverage of #EndSARS elevated police brutality to a key public concern. Similarly, Ogola (2020) saw in Kenya that ongoing reporting on post-election movements' heightened public awareness, regardless of whether the coverage was positive or negative. With Punch's greater emphasis, the Obidient movement gained more traction and visibility, strengthening its image as a powerful player in the 2023 elections.

RQ2: Prominence of Coverage (Agenda-Building Effect)

Punch did not just cover the Obidients more often, they featured stories about them on the front page and in top political sections. The Guardian, by contrast, usually placed them on inside pages or mentioned them briefly. This aligns with agenda-building theory (Lang & Lang, 1983), which suggests that when the media gives something prominent placement, it signals its significance. This influences both public and political perceptions. Supporting evidence includes Edewor (2021), who found that front-page coverage in Nigerian newspapers increased the perceived legitimacy of political candidates. Wasserman and Bosch (2021) reported similar effects with #FeesMustFall, front-page stories triggered wider national conversations. By consistently spotlighting the Obidient movement, Punch likely contributed to shaping public opinion about its importance and legitimacy.

RQ3: Tone and Framing of Coverage (Interpretive Effects)

There were also differences in tone and framing. Punch often adopted a positive, human-interest angle, portraying the movement as a genuine reform effort. The Guardian used conflict and responsibility frames, stressing chaos and questioning the movement's chances of success. This fits with Entman's (1993) framing theory, frames influence how issues are interpreted, shaping perceptions of problems and motives. Nwankwo and Okafor (2023) noted that when Nigerian media framed #EndSARS as conflict, public anxiety about activism increased. Equally, Oloruntoba and Ajibade (2022) found that human-interest frames generated more empathy for reform movements. So, Punch's supportive framing likely enhanced the Obidients' credibility, while The Guardian's skeptical tone mirrored elite concerns about the movement's stability.

RQ4: Comparative Framing Between Newspapers

Comparing both newspapers, a clear divide emerges. Punch relied heavily on issue and human-interest frames, centering on citizen motivation and the demand for better governance. The Guardian favored elite and conflict frames, focusing on internal disputes and campaign clashes.

This sort of editorial split isn't unusual. Wasserman (2020) pointed out that in South Africa, mainstream newspapers prioritized state-centric frames while alternative outlets amplified ordinary citizens' perspectives. In Nigeria, Ojebode (2019) found similar polarization in election coverage, shaped by media ownership and political biases. Ultimately, how a movement is framed depends significantly on editorial stance and ownership.

RQ5: Source Selection and Power Framing

Punch's stories featured grassroots voices, youth, volunteers, and online supporters. The Guardian, in contrast, leaned on politicians, analysts, and official sources like security agencies. This matches Gans's (1979) source hierarchy concept: elite voices typically dominate news narratives. The Guardian's reliance on authority figures echoes findings by Aladenusi & Adegbola (2021), Nigerian media tend to prioritize official sources, even in stories about citizen-led movements. Punch took a different route. By foregrounding ordinary people, as Agbaje (2023) noted, the paper made the movement appear more authentic and legitimate to readers.

However, the evidence shows both newspapers played distinct roles in shaping the agenda and framing the Obidient movement. Punch's frequent, prominent, and human-centered reporting cast the movement as a credible national force, bolstering narratives around youth engagement. The Guardian, with its less frequent and more conflict-oriented coverage, emphasized elite skepticism and electoral instability, which undermined the movement's perceived legitimacy.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the 2023 Presidential Election has similitude with the previous Presidential Elections in Nigeria from 1979 in terms of voting pattern and political behaviour. The electorates voted for their Presidents with much emphasis on ethnicity, religion and regionalism. The phenomenon seems to continue despite the development of democracy in the country. This study also shows that the 2023 Presidential Election differs in many ways from the previous Presidential Elections in the history of the country. One of the ways is that few number of political parties with a total registered number of parties up to 18, with 12 of them fielded candidates for the Presidential contest.

Many Nigerians are accustomed to electoral violence. In that respect, the 2023 election may be no different, especially because, regrettably, electoral violence and voters' suppression has already occurred. But the approach to confronting electoral violence and suppression of voters in Nigeria has changed little in recent years, despite significant shifts in the political and security context. And where there is continuity in the risks, not enough has been done to mitigate these challenges. A successful approach to mitigating election violence and suppression of voters will require a more effective response by existing institutions, particularly INEC, the police, and the security agencies, and greater innovation in reply to these contextual shifts.

Both parties and politicians need to do more to demonstrate the necessary political will and leadership to mitigate violence. Though the risks of violence are high, the picture varies considerably across the country. Examples of innovation in violence mitigation that have proven successful demonstrate there is nothing inevitable about electoral violence. Both Nigerian actors and their international partners should consider what can be done in the context of each state to address the prevailing risks. These local approaches should be pursued in addition to the broader steps that the federal and state governments, the Police, INEC, and the political parties can take to improve efforts to mitigate the risks of electoral violence.

More broadly, for electoral democracy in Nigeria to be strengthened, more than independent, trusted, and competent institutions will be required. Confidence in electoral democracy is not a one-off achievement; it requires sustaining and strengthening the quality of elections, at all levels. In addition to supporting Nigeria's institutions, there is a clear need for intensified international diplomacy to pre-empt and mitigate electoral violence and related political disputes. Regional organizations, including the Economic Community of West African States and the African Union, as well as the United States and other international supporters of the electoral process, should coordinate their approach to mitigation sufficiently in advance of the elections. In the near term, such efforts should convey expectations for political parties to effectively address their internal divisions.

Recommendations

This study therefore recommends that:

1. Media coverage should be balanced. If reporting favours one side, voters end up with a distorted view.
2. Focus on the issues. When journalists highlight genuine policy discussions, voters can judge the ideas instead of getting distracted by personalities or spectacle.
3. Maintain a neutral tone. Using emotional or charged language divides people and makes honest conversation harder.
4. Include a wider range of perspectives. Don't just feature politicians and experts, hear from everyday citizens and grassroots organizations as well.
5. Avoid sensationalism. Reporting's purpose is to inform, not to provoke. That is essential for a functioning democracy.
6. Journalists should receive proper training on recognizing bias and framing. When they understand how their reporting influences public opinion, they're less likely to unintentionally slant the story.

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